

Exercises in Collaborative Formatting

Online-Workshop at the Critical Media Lab Basel

02.02.2022

Comments and contributions are anonymised. See also the related Miro board used for collective note-taking during the session.

Session 1: Issues and Frictions

Misc

- Collaboration always already there
- What is meant by "formats"? New tools, ways of structuring, exchange formats and processes, ...?
- Adaptable "templates" as generally promising direction as a framework for creating formats
- The need for "collaboration facilitators" in projects, member who's role is to be responsible for structuring and maintaining collaboration infrastructures within a project
- The problem of collective responsibility and appropriation of shared documents
 - Documents prepared by someone else can often feel inaccessible or alien
 - Status and "rules" for how to work on a document not always clear
 - Hard to communicate or negotiate autonomy and responsibility for shared resources

Issues

- Getting "offline" information about changes/updates in a shared document, used async.
- Tension between the impulse to disconnect and the necessity to stay connected.

- Time at the screen. Maybe an obvious repercussion, but our legs, backs, eyes are suffering. Forced or timed breaks? Exercises and outside time etc.
- Impoverishment of acoustic and visual 'space', as part of relations and experience of collaboration. Everything and everyone sounds and feels like it has the same 'dimension', no big rooms, small rooms, intimate or 'loud' spaces.
- How to best to hold space when there is no space?
- Common attentions — trusting that someone is 'paying attention' and being able to signal that I am paying attention despite the 'small' presences available.
- Shared contexts – the initiation of trust and communication as transpiring through (Goffman esque?) frames, like 'funny weather we are having, no', or other things about the room, time of day, clothing, etc. that would normally situate everyone in the 'same space' (physically but also cognitively, emotionally).
- Head-shots. Something about the way people look on these interfaces, camera placement, the psychology of everyone 'looking down their noses' at one another.
- Awkward silence in Zoom sessions.

- Missing comfort, lack of feedback.
- Concentration problems. Rules and non-rules of online meetings. Disconnection from the real.
- General well-being.

- Overcome Productivity?
- Zoom meetings not only to discuss/solve/negotiate things or problems. It would be nice to discover things together – Zoom journey, collective museum tour. It seems often that Zoom meetings are the extended form of frontal teaching.
- Hanging out.
- De-personalising and de-sensitising work – making things more relativised, fun, open and less 'anxious' and 'touchy'. Somehow a good number of online interactions and tools make everything very very serious and even divisive ... hard to be informal / fun / funny / poetic / beautiful ... relates to motivation, desire, etc.

- Discussing and acknowledging different practical and mental needs of collaborators, setting and respecting the terms. Example project “Care Rider”, like a code of conduct or “needs sheet” for everyone (in meetings but also the project scope generally).
- How to establish common ground (both literally and metaphorically)?
- Before setting up common codes; encountering issues of over-stepping / writing-over / understanding how to demonstrate respect for the other's work while making space for oneself on the tool (like a shared Google doc) or the balance between presence and giving space for the other's presence.
- Tools have tutorials, but collaboration doesn't.
- Taking care of collaboration takes a lot of time and effort that is often not planned for within project work packages.
- There's often a gap between people's intentions to commit to collaborative formats and the actual participation – which is a systemic issue, not an individual shortcoming.
- Navigating hard and soft coded power structures.
- Process Documentation. I feel that the on-boarding process in tools such as Miro, or Werkbank is sometimes difficult. So, if you missed one session, it's hard to orient yourself, unless, there's some type of "metadata" informing you about the process. There's often a lack of documentation of processes helping others to get in [a tool, a shared resource, a shared doc, ...].
 - We discussed this more generally as a problem of a missing contextual layer, or “metadata” about a process
 - The status of things (like in a document). What is waste, drafts, worked on, still needed, ...
 - Responsibility for parts of a document. Being able to note who works on what for example.
 - A certain “oblivion to timeliness” (Zeitvergessenheit) of many of these tools. Many tools or documents feel like they have no history, or the tools make them feel very present. There are version histories and such, but maybe not really processual models of how things come together or in which state they are in.
- Tension between manifesting structure and queering it / keeping it dynamic

- Unshared spaces (also: headspace). How can we attune to each other (when the shared use of common spaces is missing)?
 - Physical disconnection.
 - Communicative qualifiers (e.g. how to signal urgency; how to communicate intentions; etc.). People often seem to misunderstand written communication, like you ask something and it may sound like an order. Or they feel pressured by a request but the thing itself is not that urgent as they might have understood it.
 - People are used to different tools and it's hard to introduce new ones or new conventions/habits in general.
 - Tool fatigue, learning new collaborative tools, having someone tell me about some new tool that we should all be using, feeling like I need to sign up / know about / use every tool.
 - How to disagree productively?
 - Redefining "privacy" (in the light of ubiquitous computing)
 - "Sedentariness": Needing to be at a good wifi. There is this idea that we are 'mobile' because of online collab tools, but it's not true – we have to be near a good connection, and in a kind of 'appropriate environment' for a meeting/call.
 - Schedule and deadline formality / informality. There is a lot of 'sliding around' of meetings because of the disappearance or 'convenience' of geographies. Similarly I find deadlines, as everything transpires online, to be a bit less 'concrete' when things are negotiated solely online. I'm not sure if I like this or don't like this.
 - Digital leftovers. Collections of links, leftovers of meetings. Losing overview.
 - Collecting all the things mentioned in a meeting, links posted to the chat, to keep or share after a meeting. (mentioned in relation to Whirlpool)
 - Collectively collecting pop up associations.
 - Tool packages. Each collaboration requires a different 'tool package' (usually combining 2, 3, 4 different apps and online tools). Often you need to login with a different institutional account for each, search emails to find links to the latest doc etc. Nightmare to remember and keep track. → (Whirlpool = great solution?) → Sharing 'tool packages' with different teams, with a set of internal rules and agreements of participants.
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Session 2: New Formats

Brief notes of the presentations of new collaboration "formats" discussed in smaller groups.

Group 1: How to make a process traceable and interoperable?

- Do tools for collaboration offer all needed features or are they just an expansion of single-user tools for several users? Do the tools especially support specific practices of collaborative work? [Seems much steered by my talking about it]
- Define different lines of action
 - Temporality, categorization etc. (in comments for example, where you get to say something about the status of your contribution to a document)
 - Interplay of online and offline activities
- [KOM](#) (Astrom&Zimmer), Git-hub inspired tools such as [Abstract](#)

Group 2: Meeting in/formalities

- Breaking up the Zoom / Meeting
- Code of (in)formalities for specific kinds of meetings [Etiquette]
- define purpose of meetings
- adjust format of the meeting accordingly
- break meeting up into parts (even more)

Group 3: Missing shared context

- Sharing new norms – in terms of what we feel, do and don't do
- Routines to expose context, e.g. at the beginning of a meeting
- Heads up displays that give 'context', mood...
- A special meeting regularly that is 'about' context (or sharing context, 'ice cream' sessions, ...).
- Meta-data and information about seemingly 'unimportant' stuff...
- Pasting the weather in the chat at the beginning of a call
- Tools that keeps you interested/excited: off-topic channels, social media-like streams, being able to mess with the environment (including Zoom background switching, filters etc.?).
- Find a way to keep and express joy
- Click-engagement / movement engagement (real time likes)
- Attention – feedback – 'keep alive' techniques?

Group 4: How to set-up a common ground?

- Onboarding process: How to involve group members and set up the workflow?
- Informal chat on needs & expectations & rhythms of work & restrictions & conditions
- Sharing of personal processes
- Continual social check-ins
- Share awareness of contracts and maybe other obligations
- Other idea: Test out different working flows: according to lunar calendar or cosmic energy or ... (So work according to a given structure; or have a week for meetings, another for writing, ...)